

Archives of Neurosurgery in Africa

The Official Journal of the
Nigerian Academy of Neurological Surgeons (NANS)

Publication Details

The Archives of Neurosurgery in Africa is a leading peer review Journal for scientific research pertaining to the field of neurosurgery. It is the official Journal of the Nigerian Academy of Neurological Surgeons (NANS) which publishes original research on several neurological conditions including surgical disorders of brain, spine, spinal cord and peripheral nerves. It is a biannual publication.

Aims and Scope

To communicate unique or unusual clinical cases encountered across all fields of neurosurgery.

To report individual results of new research, surgical approaches and techniques.

To complement the research findings and reviews published in Journals of Neurosurgery with clinical data and cases.

To promote greater exchange of information between the specialties and subspecialties related neurosurgery.

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Publishers: Samd Davies Publishers, His Grace Villa, Plot 4, Adenekan-Oyejide Street, Olorunredo Layout, Kuelu, Olode, New Ife Road, Ibadan, P. O. Box 27411, Agodi, Ibadan, Nigeria.

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Archives of Neurosurgery in Africa
The Official Journal of the
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Editorial

I am very delighted that this inaugural issue of our Journal is finally published. I thank the previous Editorial Team for laying the foundation for the take off of the Journal.

Furthermore, I thank the various authors for believing in the Editorial Team to produce a quality Journal despite the glaring challenges; on behalf of the Editorial Team, I appreciate your trust. We are determined to sustain the efforts and we look forward to receiving your further contributions in future.

I also thank the various reviewers for responding to our requests to review the articles. As you are aware, we will continue to knock on your doors to achieve the goals of the Journal.

COVID-19 came shortly after we took over the editorial task of the Journal. This maiden issue has two articles on this ravaging pandemic and the readers will find the views expressed by Abiodun Okunlola in his article interesting. It will be great to have your feedback.

We will continue to improve on the editorial assignment so that the Journal will soon score exceedingly high in the various performance indices.

I sincerely thank the Editorial Team for the cooperation and encouragement. In addition, I thank the Academy for the confidence they have in us.

Sincerely,

Augustine A. Adeolu
Editor -in-Chief

Goodwill Message

From the President

On behalf of the Honorary Presidents, Past Presidents, and the entire membership of the Nigerian Academy of Neurological Surgeons (NANS), I am delighted to announce the publication of the inaugural issue of the Archives of Neurosurgery in Africa Journal.

This Journal has been in the making for many years. This is a necessity from the growth being experienced in the numbers of Nigerian Neurosurgeons as well as in the quality of papers presented at our annual meetings. We hope that with adequate and sustained patronage from our members and others, we will maintain regular publication of the Journal and produce at least two issues per year. I will encourage all our new fellows to write up their thesis and publish in the Journal. As much as possible too, top rated paper presentations in our conferences will also be published in the Journal. We also solicit that we bring more practice-based articles, very important case reports/case series, relevant and critical review papers and prospective randomized studies/clinical trials for consideration for publication so that in the very nearest future, the Journal can score high in various performance measures, be listed in appropriate sites, be ranked high as well as obtain impact factor.

I will like to thank our Editor-in-Chief and his team for working tirelessly to ensure this inaugural issue is produced.

Long live NANS.

Thank you.

Professor Edward. O. Komolafe

President

Nigerian Academy of Neurological Surgeons (NANS)

Pattern of congenital craniospinal anomalies among neurosurgical patients in a tertiary hospital in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: Congenital craniospinal anomalies are being reported more often than in the past by various neurosurgical centres in Africa. This study evaluates the patterns of various craniospinal anomalies and their possible risk factors in a new neurosurgical centre in Nigeria.

Methods: The study included all patients with congenital craniospinal anomalies managed at the LAUTECH Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Nigeria, from January 2013- December 2015. Frequency and pattern of these anomalies were recorded. All patients were assessed for associated anomalies. Data related to age, gender, type of anomaly, location and maternal details including soci-economic class, febrile illness in pregnancy and drugs used in pregnancy were recorded on a pre-designed proforma. Cranial CT/MRI and TFUSS were obtained according to the type of the lesion. Surgical interventions were performed as required.

Results: Nineteen patients with congenital craniospinal anomalies were seen during the study period. Ten of the cases were male (52.6%). The most common anomaly observed was hydrocephalus (n:10, 52.6%) which is either in isolation (n:7,70%) or combined with spina bifida(n:3,30%), followed by spina bifida which was found in 5 patients (36.8%). Of the spina bifida, myelomeningocele accounted for (n:4,80%). Encephalocele was seen in (n:3, 17.6) and they were all occipital. There was a case of craniosynostosis. Majority of patients with hydrocephalus had VP shunt (n:7, 70%) while 1(10%) had ETV. Surgical repair was performed for the neural tube defect cases. None of the mothers had peri-conceptual folic acid supplementation, three (15.8%) of them had febrile illness in pregnancy while 1 (5.3%) had exposure to irradiation. Four (21.1%) of the mothers used anti-malarias early in pregnancy. None had family history of CNS anomalies.

Conclusion: Congenital craniospinal anomalies represent a significant group of neurosurgical conditions seen at our centre. Public awareness of peri-conceptual use of folic acid to reduce the risk of mothers having babies with congenital CNS anomalies need to be promoted.

Keywords:

Neurosurgery, Africa, Brain, Spinal Cord, Malformation

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Introduction

Neural tube defects (NTDs) are a group of complex congenital malformation of the brain and spinal cord that arise due to failure of closure of neural tube during embryogenesis.¹ In this malformation, there is abnormal closure of neural fold in the 3rd and 4th week of intra-uterine life and the structures commonly involved in its formation are meninges, vertebrae, skin and muscle.²

NTDs are a major health problem worldwide.^{3,4} With the dramatic decrease in infant mortality due to improvement in the control of infections and malnutrition related disorders, chronic disabling conditions are an emerging challenge facing developing and industrialized nations.⁵ In the past, the causes of the infant mortality used to be traced mostly to the prevalence of infectious diseases. The introduction of new antibiotics, improved obstetrics care and advances made in the field of preventive medicine and immunology have arrested the tendency and it was found that death in infancy was more due to malformation than infectious diseases.⁶ This however, may not be true for developing countries like Nigeria.

There is a large variation in the incidence of NTDs in different parts of the world and at different periods.⁷ NTDs are found in about 1:1000 pregnancies in the U.S.⁸ In UK the prevalence of NTDs in absence of selective abortions or antenatal diagnosis is 3-4 per 1000 births.⁹ The incidence of NTDs is unknown in many parts of Nigeria because of the dearth of literature reporting NTDs in the country. However, Adeyemo *et al* reported a rate of 22.5% for spina bifida of the cases of major congenital malformations seen in Ibadan, in the western part of Nigeria.¹⁰

The birth of an infant with major malformations, whether diagnosed ante-natally or not, evokes an emotional parental response.¹¹ NTDs are sometimes associated with other abnormalities such as vertebral, anorectal, cardiac, tracheoesophageal, renal and limb abnormalities (VACTERL). Fetal anomaly scanning is the most

powerful approach available for reducing the birth prevalence of infants with serious congenital abnormalities and increasing the chances of survival for those who are born.¹²

The aim of this study was to determine the pattern, risk factors and outcomes of craniospinal anomalies among children admitted to a teaching hospital in south west Nigeria.

Patients and Methods

This was a prospective study of patients with congenital craniospinal anomalies admitted in the Neurological Surgery Division, Department of Surgery, LAUTECH Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Nigeria, which is a referral hospital for patients requiring specialised neurosurgical care.

The records of patients with gross congenital Central Nervous System (CNS) anomalies admitted over a period of 3 years (January 2013 to December 2015) were kept in an electronic database and analysed. Variables recorded and analysed included age, gender, mother's antenatal details, level of education and social economic status, the type and site of lesions, associated congenital malformations, investigations performed, length of hospital stay as well as outcomes following care.

Cranial Computerized Tomography (CT)/Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Transfontanelle Ultrasound (TFUSS) and spinal X-rays were performed depending on the lesion type. Patients with amenable anomalies were operated after proper investigations.

Results

A total of 19 patients with CNS anomalies were admitted. Average age in months at presentation was 11.4 months (Range: 4 hrs-20 years). Ten (52.6%) were males and all were products of term gestation. Age at conception for most of the women was 26-35 years {12(63.2%)}. Identified maternal risk factors included low socio-economic status {13(68.4%)}, and low educational status {11(57.9%)}. None of the women used periconceptional folic acid. Febrile illnesses in pregnancy occurred in 3(15.8%) of the mothers

Table 1:

Distribution of craniospinal anomalies

Anomaly	No (%)
Hydrocephalus	10(52.63%)
Myelomeningocele	4(21.05%)
Meningocele	1(5.26%)
Encephalocele	3(15.79%)
Craniosynostosis	1(5.26%)
Total	19(100%)

Figure 1. A. Abnormal head enlargement and craniofacial proportion in a child with hydrocephalus. **B.** Cranial CT showing panventriculomegaly in hydrocephalus. **C.** Occipital encephalocele. **D.** Post-op picture of child pictured in **C** with the happy mother

while 1(5.3%) had exposure to radiation (X-rays). 4(21.1%) of the mothers used anti-malarial drugs (Chloroquine and Fansidar) during pregnancy. (Table 2)

Table 2:

Maternal risk factors

Maternal Risk Factor	No (%)
Low socio-economic status	13(68.4%)
Low educational status	11(57.9%)
Lack of periconceptional folate supplementation	19(100.0%)
Febrile illness in pregnancy	3(15.8%)
Exposure to radiation	4(21.1%)

Eight (42.1%) of the mothers had prenatal ultrasound scan. Of these, only 3 (37.5%) suggested craniospinal anomalies.

Of the diagnosed anomalies, hydrocephalus constituted majority of the cases {10 (52.6%)} (Table 1). Of these, 8(80%) were non- communicating and due mainly to aqueductal stenosis and posterior fossa cyst (Dandy-Walker Malformation). Spina bifida (myelomeningocele and meningocele) was seen in 5(26.3%) cases. Of these, myelomeningocele accounted for 4(80%) of the cases. Concerning the site of the spina bifida, 3(60%) were lumbosacral, 1(20%) was sacral and 1 (20%) was lumbar. Three (60%) had intact sac while the sac was ruptured in 40% of the cases of spina bifida. Limb weaknesses and loss of sphincteric control were found in the children with myelomeningocele. Three (17.6%) of the patients had encephalocele and they were all located in the occipital region. One of the study subjects had syndromic craniosynostosis.

Associated anomalies were seen in 6(31.6%). These were talipes equinovarus

{3(50%)}, cardiac defect {1(16.7%)}, syndactyl {1(16.7%)} and umbilical hernia {1(16.7%)}.

Transfontanelle ultrasound was done in 9(47.4%) of the patients. Of these, 6(66.7%) showed triventriculomegaly suggestive of obstructive hydrocephalus. Cranial CT was done in 7(36.8%) while MRI was done in 2(10.5%) of the cases. Almost all the cases had operative intervention 15(78.9%).

Ventriculoperitoneal (VP) shunt was done for 7(36.8%). All the cases with encephalocele had surgical repair and 4(21.1%) had repair of myelomeningocele. Strip craniectomies and cranial vault reconstruction was done for the case of craniosynostosis.

The average length of hospital stay was 1 week (Range: 5 days - 2.5weeks). Ten (52.6%) of the cases had less than one week stay. Six (85.7%) of the VP shunt babies had good control of their head size following surgery and all the operated cases of spina bifida and encephalocele had good cosmetic outcome. (Fig. 1: illustrative cases)

Discussion

Birth defects are a major cause of perinatal and neonatal deaths and incidence of NTDs is variable depending upon the ethnicity, geographical location and gender.¹³ Age at conception for most of the mothers (63.2%) was 26-35 years, this is at variance with most of the other studies which observed that congenital anomalies were more common in babies of young mothers (age <20 years) and again in mothers aged 35 years and above.^{14,15}

In our study, most of the cases (52.6%) were males, which is similar to the findings by Huma Mushtaq *et al* who reported 57% males in their study and Brohi A R *et al* in which 62.5% of cases were males.^{16,17} Higher rates of NTDs have been reported in populations with lower socioeconomic status.¹⁸ In our study, 68.4% of the mothers belonged to the lower socioeconomic status. This is comparable with the findings of

Fauzia Butt *et al* in which 70% of the mothers were of low socioeconomic status.¹⁹ Majority of the mothers (57.9%) also had low level of education which may suggest poor health seeking behaviour and delayed ante natal care visits.

In the United States of America, the recommendation is that all women of child bearing age who are capable of becoming pregnant should take 0.4mg of folic acid daily in other to reduce the risk of the foetus developing an NTD.²⁰ Also in Britain, a woman who plans to become pregnant is placed on folate (4mg) supplementation daily from one month before conception to the 12th week of pregnancy.²¹ However, we observed that none of the mothers in our study had peri-conceptual folic acid intake and many of them commenced antenatal visits after 3 months of pregnancy. This was similar to the findings of Rabin *et al* and Idowu *et al* in which none of the mothers used periconceptual folic acid.^{22,23}

A “flu” or cold syndrome or febrile illness in the first trimester has been associated with a two to threefold increase in risk for NTD. In our study 15.8% of the mothers had febrile illness during pregnancy. Of all the craniospinal anomalies, the commonest anomaly noted in most of the studies is hydrocephalus.^{25,26}

We also noted hydrocephalus in the majority of the cases in our study (52.6%), which is in agreement with what was found by Huma Mushtaq *et al* (66.25%) and Kumar *et al* (58.8%).^{16,27} Brohi *et al* and Khattak *et al* reported most of their cases to be hydrocephalus with 42.18% and 45.6% respectively.^{17,28} We found 80% of the hydrocephalus to be non-communicating and due to aqueductal stenosis. Sixty percent of the cases had VP shunt and 10% had ETV. All the operated cases had good control of head size and improved neurological functions.

In this study, spina bifida (myelomeningocele and meningocele) accounted for 26.3% of all the cases. This compares favourably with the study of Huma Mushtaq which showed spina bifida in 14.37% of their cases but at variance with the study of Brohi *et al* which had

spina bifida in 42.18% of their cases.^{16,17} Of the spina bifida cases, myelomeningocele accounted for 80 % in this study which is in agreement with the study by Uba *et al* in which 79.6% of the spina bifida were myelomeningocele.²⁴

Out of the cases of spina bifida, 60% were lumbosacral which agrees with the findings of A F Uba *et al* and also with studies from north America but at variance with the preponderance of thoracolumbar found in many studies from other countries.^{24,29,30} The sac was ruptured in 60% of the cases which is in concordance with the study of Uba *et al* where 69.4% of the cases had ruptured and sometimes ulcerated sac.²⁴ This may be due to delay in presentation at the hospital. Hydrocephalus was associated with 60% of the spina bifida. This is at variance with 85-90% incidence reported worldwide.²⁹ These cases probably had Chiari II malformation but this could not be confirmed as MRI was not done. The incidence of paraplegia, 40%, and incontinence, 80%, compares favourably with findings elsewhere. Encephalocele was noted in 17.6% of the cases and all of them were occipital. This was slightly more than what was found by Brohi *et al* and Huma Mushtaq *et al* (10.93% and 5.6% respectively). We had a case of craniosynostosis (5.26%) which is in agreement with the 3.12% reported by Huma mushtaq *et al*.¹⁷ We found no case of anencephaly in our study and this agrees with the study of Binitie OP, probably because many of those babies die shortly after birth.³¹

The associated birth defects were mostly talipes equinovarus which accounted for 50% of the defects. This is similar to the findings by Binitie OP in northern part of Nigeria.³¹

Our results probably underestimated the number of craniospinal anomalies in our region possibly due to non-referral of some cases or due to mothers abandoning their babies with congenital anomalies to die as was seen in one of our cases of myelomeningocele.

In addition, the average age at presentation (11.4months) is late. Considering that most of the anomalies are obvious and/or present at birth, delayed presentation, as detailed

by Rabiū *et al* for congenital CNS malformations, may be responsible for the low number of cases reported in this study and many of the affected children in our community might have succumbed to their disease(s).³²

It is our belief that these cases are still widespread due to lack of periconceptional use of folic acid. More needs to be done in public enlightenment on the use of folic acid in pregnancy. Efforts should be placed on periconceptional usage rather than the practice of mid-trimester usage.

Conclusion

Congenital Craniospinal anomalies represent an important group of neurosurgical conditions seen at our centre. Public awareness of periconceptional use of folic acid to reduce the risk of mothers having babies with congenital CNS anomalies need to be promoted.

Sources of support: Nil

Conflict of interest: Nil

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Submission Date

18/10/2020

Acceptance Date

13/12/2020

Efficacy of Scotchcast as external orthosis for spinal instability

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ABSTRACT

Background: Management of spinal instability with external orthoses affords the patients to be managed non-operatively with the additional advantage of outpatient care. This study was designed to determine the efficacy of Scotchcast as external orthosis for spinal instability.

Methods: Patients' data were collected prospectively and patients who had spinal instability with minimal spinal deformity and incomplete neurological deficits were included. Minerva jacket was applied for cervical spinal instability and thoracolumbar spinal orthosis (TLSO) was applied for thoracic and lumbar spinal instability using Scotchcast. Primary outcome measures were the ability of the cast to retain its stabilizing effect and healing of the spinal instability as demonstrated by dynamic X-ray. Presence of pressure sore from the cast was used as a secondary outcome measure.

Results: Sixty patients were included in the study. Age range was 2 to 77 years. Male to female ratio was 7:3. Sixteen patients with cervical spinal instability had Minerva jacket while the remaining patients with thoracic and lumbar spinal instability had TLSO. Forty-six patients used the orthoses for 3 months while 13 patients used their orthoses for 4 to 6 months. Fifty-five (92%) patients had satisfactory spinal stabilization. One patient had a minimal kyphotic deformity and three patients had persistent spinal instability. There were no patients with neurological deterioration during the review. All the orthoses were intact at the time of their removal.

Conclusion: The use of Scotchcast as external orthosis is a valid option in the management of selected patients with spinal instability with a good outcome.

Keywords:

Scotchcast, External orthotic, Spinal instability, Stabilization

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Introduction

White and Panjabi defined spinal instability as the inability of the spine to withstand the physiological load.¹ Management of spinal instability with external orthoses affords the patients to be managed non-operatively with an additional advantage of outpatient care especially if the patients have a functional incomplete injury or no neurological deficits. Early mobilization without adequate internal or external fixation may allow an unacceptable kyphosis to develop at the site of the fracture.² In patients with an incomplete neurological lesion, early activity without stability may compromise a spinal canal that is already narrowed by haematoma, oedema or bony fragment, and cause further trauma to the cord.³ Effective treatment must minimize the disruption caused by the patient's absence from family and job as well as ensure satisfactory healing in a good position. Despite fears that instability and deformities may occur, the time for immobilization for these fractures has gradually reduced. Mobilization with external bracing has been employed far earlier than previously stated.^{3,4}

Plaster of Paris (POP) was often used in the past as external orthosis for the spine but it was abandoned largely because it is often weak before the end of the stabilizing period, thus, necessitating recurrent reinforcement. Halo brace for cervical instability is an improvement over Minerva jacket which used to be made with POP. So also, newer agents were used to replace TLSO made from POP. Many of these materials are not only costly but are also scarce in the third world. Thus, we have adopted the use of the Scotchcast to produce the Minerva jacket and TLSO for our patients who need prolonged immobilization as a form of non-operative management of spinal instability. This study was, therefore, designed to determine the efficacy of Scotchcast as an external orthosis for spinal instability.

Patients and Methods

Patients who had established or anticipated spinal instability with minimal spinal deformity and

incomplete neurological deficits were included in the study and those with complete neurological deficits were excluded. Minerva jacket was applied for the cervical spine and thoracolumbar spinal orthosis (TLSO) was used for thoracolumbar instability. The patients were subsequently discharged home for follow-up in the clinic. The patients had dynamic x-rays out of cast three months after the application of the spinal orthoses. The primary outcome measures were the ability of the cast to retain its stabilizing effect at the end of the immobilization period and healing of the spinal instability as demonstrated by dynamic x-rays when the cast was removed. Presence of pressure sore related to the use of the cast was used as a secondary outcome measure.

Results

Sixty patients were included in the study. The age range was 2 to 77 years with a peak at third and fourth decades. The male: female ratio was 7:3. The most common indication for the use of spinal orthosis was traumatic spinal injury (37 patients; 61.7%) followed by tuberculosis of the spine (10 patients; 16.7%). The other indications are as shown in Table 1. Among the patients with

Table 1:
Aetiologies of spinal instability

Aetiologies	Frequency	Percentage
Trauma	37	61.7
Tuberculosis of the spine	10	16.7
Neoplasia	7	11.7
Degenerative spine disease	5	8.3
Congenital malformation	1	1.7
Total	60	100

neoplasms, three had multiple myeloma, two had haemangioma of the vertebral body and metastasis to the spine occurred in two patients.

The level of spinal instability was cervical spine (16; 26.7%), upper thoracic spine (4; 6.7%),

Table 2:
Level of spinal instability

Level of spinal instability	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Cervical spine	16	26.7
Upper cervical spine	7	
Sub-axial cervical spine	9	
Upper thoracic spine	4	6.7
Mid-thoracic spine	8	13.3
Lower thoracic spine	15	25
Thoracolumbar spine	3	5
Lumbar spine	14	23.3
Total	60	100

Figure 1. Minerva jacket

mid-thoracic spine (8; 13.3%), lower thoracic spine (15; 25%), thoracolumbar spine (3; 5%) and lumbar spine (14; 23.3%) (Table 2). The upper cervical spinal lesions (7 patients) comprise of un-displaced type 2 and type 3 odontoid peg fractures and Hangman fractures. Sub-axial cervical spine instabilities (9 patients) were mainly vertebral burst fractures and one patient had C5/6 anterior subluxation with unilateral facet fracture. The thoracic and lumbar spinal instability comprises of burst fractures with an intact posterior element and no significant spinal canal compromise.

Sixteen patients with cervical spinal instability had Minerva jacket (figure 1). The patients with thoracic and lumbar spinal instability had thoracolumbar spinal orthosis (TLSO) which were hanged on the shoulders in patients with upper thoracic spinal instability (4 patients) and combined with hip spica (figure 2) for 2 patients with spinal instability below L2. The TLSO were bivalved and straps were applied in 11 patients (figure 3).

Forty-six (76.7%) patients wore their orthoses for 3 months and thirteen (21.7%) patients wore theirs for 4 to 6 months. The latter group included the patients with TB spine and multiple myeloma on chemotherapy. One (1.7%) patient was lost to follow up. The spinal orthoses were used as primary care in 49 (81.7%) patients, post-operative care in 10(16.7%) patients and

Figure 2. TLSO with hip spica

Figure 3. Bivalved TLSO

Figure 4. a. Hangman fracture at presentation

b and c. flexion and extension images taken 2 months post trauma after the removal of the Minerva jacket

post failed Gardner Wells Traction (GWT) in 1(1.7%) patient. Fifty-five (92%) patients had a satisfactory bone union and spinal stabilization on dynamic x-ray after the removal of the orthoses (figure 4). One (1.7%) patient had a minimal kyphotic deformity and three patients (5%) had persistent spinal instability. The latter included a 32-year old man with TB spine (L3 vertebral body destruction), a 50-year-old man with multiple myeloma (L4 vertebral body fracture) and a 50-year old man with C5/6 anterior subluxation and unilateral facet fracture. One (1.7%) patient had skin excoriation. There was no neurological deterioration in any of the patients. None of the orthoses showed evidence of weakness or fracture at the time of removal.

Discussion

Spinal instability affects all age groups.⁴ There was a significant male preponderance in this study probably because trauma was the most common cause of spinal instability in the series. Other aetiological factors include tuberculosis of the spine, neoplasia, degenerative spine disease and congenital malformation.⁵ Previous studies focussed on either regional spinal instability (e. g cervical or thoracolumbar) or aetiological factors involved.^{2,5}

Spinal orthoses have been employed in the management of both traumatic and non-traumatic spinal instability with favourable outcome.^{5,6} The role of spinal orthoses in the post-operative management of spinal instability is complementary most especially when rigid fixation cannot be guaranteed.⁷ There have been tremendous advances in the field of spine surgery over the last three decades and most implant failures are the result of a poor implant and/or patient selection.⁸ Early internal fixation has been recommended for traumatic upper cervical spinal instability.⁹ Other authors have highlighted the role of external orthoses in the management of the upper cervical spinal instability in selected cases.¹⁰ All patients with upper cervical spinal instability in our series had Minerva jacket with satisfactory bone union and stability after the removal of the external orthoses and there was no neurological deterioration. The outcome of management of the sub-axial cervical spinal instability with Minerva jacket was satisfactory except in one patient with C_{5/6} subluxation and unilateral facet fracture who had persistent spinal instability on dynamic x-ray after removal of the jacket. Facet fracture and/or dislocation was associated with failure of conservative management of cervical spinal instability in the previous studies.¹¹ The efficacy of Minerva jacket

in the management of the spinal instability has been shown to be similar to that of Halo vest.^{12,13}

TLSO has been widely used in the management of thoracic and lumbar spinal instability with various modifications depending on the level of the spinal instability: hanged for upper thoracic instability, with hip spica for lower lumbar spinal instability.^{6,7} Scotchcast has replaced plaster of Paris (POP) cast due to its durability, x-ray penetration, lightweight and comfortability.¹² It is cheaper than the factory-made orthoses and is a good alternative to the conventional factory-made Halo vest and TLSO in the management of spinal instability most especially in the low resource setting.

Patients with impaired sensation may not appreciate the development of wound under the cast in the event of a pressure sore. This necessitated their exclusion from this study. The advantage of this important exclusion criterion is obvious in the study with only one patient showing evidence of skin excoriation.

Conclusion

An external spinal orthosis using Scotchcast is a valid option in the management of both traumatic and non-traumatic spinal instability with a good outcome.

Conflict of interest: Authors declared no conflict of interest

Funding: No external funding

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Submission Date

30/09/2020

Acceptance Date

13/12/2020

Impact of dedicated trauma Intensive Care Unit Management on outcome of traumatic brain injury at National Trauma Centre, Abuja

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ABSTRACT

Background/Objective: Traumatic brain injury (TBI) is the most common cause of intensive care unit (ICU) admission worldwide. Unlike the practice in many developed countries, most ICU units in Nigeria admit and manage multispecialty cases. A previous study from our institution found a mortality rate of 68.4% among head injured patients managed in our multispecialty ICU. The aim of this study is to evaluate the effect of dedicated trauma ICU management on the outcome of patients with TBI.

Method: This is a one-year retrospective cohort review of patients with TBI managed in our trauma ICU. The medical records of patients with TBI managed in the 12 bedded trauma ICU were studied including demographic characteristics, mechanism of injury, Glasgow Coma Score (GCS) at admission, neuroimaging and interventions. The primary outcome was the Glasgow Outcome Scale at discharge from the hospital.

Result: Among 134 patients admitted into the trauma ICU within this period, 88 (65%) had TBI. Among patients with TBI, 74 (84.1%) sustained severe head injury and 12 (13.6 %) had moderate head injury. Their ages ranged from 3 months to 78 years, with a median age of 35 years. The Male to Female ratio was 4.5:1. Motor vehicular Accident (MVA) was the most common cause of TBI. The mean injury to presentation interval was 23.98hrs, while the mean emergency presentation to ICU admission interval was 37.98hrs. The overall mortality rate was 47%, with the highest mortality (87.8%, n=36) seen in patients with severe TBI.

Conclusion: A modest reduction in mortality rate was observed compared to a previous study from our center.

Keywords:

Traumatic Brain Injury, Trauma ICU, Management, Outcome

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Introduction

Traumatic brain injury (TBI) is a public health problem worldwide. Current trend reveals a global TBI burden approaching epidemic proportions.¹ TBI is the most common cause of intensive care unit (ICU) admission, accounting for a great percentage of ICU morbidity and mortality despite invasive and aggressive therapy and monitoring.^{2,3} The primary role of ICU admission and treatment in acute TBI is the prevention of secondary brain damage. Primary brain injury sustained at the time of impact is usually followed by secondary pathological processes such as brain oedema, intracranial haemorrhage and raised intracranial pressure resulting from hypoxia, hypercapnia, hypertension, hypotension, hyperglycaemia, hypoglycaemia and dyselectrolytaemia.^{2,4} Measures that ameliorate or mitigate the development of secondary brain insults, such as early diagnosis and prompt ICU admission with the institution of recommended TBI management protocol have been found to be associated with improved outcome.⁵ ICU management has been shown to be a key factor impacting survival following severe TBI.⁶

Therefore, there is much to be gained by optimizing the critical care of the severely injured patients, through a specialized ICU model, with advanced training of staff in trauma critical care. Most ICU in Nigeria lack this capacity, and operate a mixed; medical and surgical ICU system of admission and care for critically ill patients, unlike standard practice in developed countries of the world. A previous study from this same hospital by Ohaegbulam *et al*, in 2005 found a mortality rate of 68.4% among head injured patients admitted in our multispecialty ICU before the establishment of a specialized trauma ICU.⁷ Studies from centers in Lagos, Ilorin and Enugu with multispecialty ICU models have reported mortality rates of 77.3%, 70% and 54% respectively among TBI patients.^{2,5,7} The aim of

this study is to evaluate the impact of dedicated trauma ICU management on the outcome of care in patients with TBI in our center.

Methodology

Study design

This is a retrospective cohort study on the outcome of TBI care within a dedicated trauma intensive care unit.

Inclusion criteria: Patients with traumatic brain injury admitted and managed in the trauma centre ICU of the National Trauma Centre Abuja over one-year period from February 2015 and February 2016.

Outcome measure: The primary outcome measure was the Glasgow Outcome Score (GOS) at the time of discharge from the hospital.

ICU Model of Critical Care Delivery

The trauma ICU in our center operates as a dedicated ICU for the management of critically injured trauma patients requiring intensive care and monitoring. Our ICU protocol is a “modified” open intensive care unit model; where the primary managing surgeon and a dedicated critical care anesthesiologist co-manage and assume shared responsibility for the provision of critical care service to the patients. The nursing staff in the ICU are certified, trauma intensive care nurses. The ICU is equipped with eight ventilators, multi-parameter monitor, invasive and non-monitoring and Arterial Blood Gas (ABG) monitors. There is also intracranial pressure monitoring device used for selected patients who can afford the cost.

The severity of injury at admission was classified using the Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score at admission into three categories. Patients with a GCS score of 3-8 were classified as severe TBI, patients with a GCS score of 9-12 were classified as moderate TBI and patients with GCS score of 13-15 were classified as mild TBI. The

admission of patients into the ICU followed standard protocol as recommended by the Brain Trauma foundation based on the severity of injury and the need for acute life-sustaining physiological support. After initial resuscitation at the Emergency room department, the patients with severe TBI (GCS < 8) or moderate TBI with respiratory distress from chest injury requiring ventilator support, were intubated with endotracheal tube and placed on a mobile ventilator and a multi-parameter monitor in the emergency room. Haemodynamically stable patients were immediately transferred for brain CT scan and neurosurgical intervention was carried out on those with intracranial haematomas requiring surgical evacuation, while patients with non-surgical lesions were transferred immediately to ICU. First tier management of intracranial pressure was instituted in all patients including, nursing the patients 30° head up, sedation, analgesics, seizure prophylaxis with intravenous phenytoin and ventilatory support. All patients had continuous monitoring of electrocardiograph reading c (ECG), blood pressure, oxygen saturation and or blood gases, urine output and pupillary changes or reactivity. Patients care givers were counsel for Intracranial Pressure (ICP) monitoring and patients who can afford, had the Camino® ICP monitors (Camino Laboratories, San Diego, California, USA) placed for ICP monitoring. Patients with clinical and or radiological features of raised ICP or whose ICP monitor indicated a raised ICP were commenced on intravenous 20% mannitol (loading dose and maintenance dose for 24 – 48hours) patients who continued to deteriorate or had worsen/persistent features of raised ICP eventually had decompressive craniectomy.

Data collection and analysis

All patients with severe and moderate TBI requiring ventilatory support admitted and managed in the trauma ICU with the above

protocol within the study period were included in the study. The medical records of the patients were retrieved and data collection was done using a designed proforma which was completed by the research team members. Information regarding age and gender, GCS at admission, mechanism of injury, time interval between injury and admission as well as time interval between presentation and ICU admission, neuroimaging findings, other associated injuries and complications was obtained. The outcome of patient care was assessed using the Glasgow outcome Score (GOS) categorized as: (1.) Death, (2.) Vegetative, (3.) severe disability, (4.) Moderate disability, (5.) Good recovery.

A descriptive analysis of all the data was performed by calculating means and standard deviations for continuous variables and proportions for categorical variables.

Result

One hundred and thirty four patients were admitted into the trauma ICU within this period. Eighty-eight of these patients had TBI. Among the 88 patients with TBI, 74 had severe TBI, while 12 had moderate TBI. The age range was 3 months to 78 years, with a median age of 35years

Table 1:
Age and sex distribution

Age group	Gender		Total
	Male	Female	
0 -10	7	5	12
11 – 20	5	2	7
21 – 30	17	2	19
31 – 40	15	4	19
41 – 50	13	1	14
51 – 60	5	1	6
> 60	4	1	5
Unknown	6	0	6
Total	72	16	88

(Table 1). There were more male patients than female across all age groups with male to female ratio of 4.5:1. Although the incidence in female showed a reduction with increasing age, among males however, the incidence increased with age with a peak at 20 – 40 year age range. There was significant difference in the age distribution between the two sexes (Chi square: $X^2 = 4.309$, $p=0.038$, $df=??$) Motor vehicular crashes were the most common cause of TBI accounting for 34 cases, followed by pedestrian injuries which occurred among 23 patients (TABLE 2). The overall mortality from this study was 41% with

the highest mortality rate seen in severe TBI, in male patients and in patients between 31 – 40 years of age (Chi square with trend = 0.060, $p=0.806$), there was no significant difference in outcome between males and females. The average time interval between presentation to the emergency and ICU admission was 37.98hrs, while the average time interval between injury and presentation was 23.98hrs. The time interval between presentation and ICU admission and mortality showed that no patient was admitted into the ICU in less than an hour of presentation, majority of the patients were admitted into the ICU between 6 and 24hours of presentation to the resuscitation unit of the hospital. Patients who were admitted into ICU between 12 - 24hours and after 24hours recorded mortality of 11 and 12 respectively.

Table 2:
Aetiology distribution

Aetiology	Frequency	Percentage
Motor vehicle crashes	34	38.6
Motorcycle crashes	17	19.3
Pedestrian	23	26.1
Fall from height	5	5.7
Assault	2	2.2
Bomb blast	1	1.1
Others	6	6.8
Total	88	100.0

Discussion

Traumatic brain injury has been a major cause of mortality and morbidity worldwide, especially in children and young adults and has consistently been a difficult problem in Intensive Care Units (ICU).⁸ The trauma physician has little or no influence on the severity of primary brain injury

Figure 1. Outcome distribution

Figure 2. Glasgow Outcome Score: Sex distribution

Figure 3. Age mortality distribution

as at the time of injury, however, the impact of secondary brain injury can be minimized if appropriate therapies are implemented in time.⁸ The basic principle in the care and treatment of severe TBI is the early identification and prompt

treatment of factors that may worsen primary injury leading to secondary brain damage. A dedicated trauma ICU management for patients with TBI provides a platform for achieving this level of care. This study shows that TBI remains the major cause of trauma ICU admissions which

Figure 4. Injury severity and mortality

Figure 5. ICU admission interval and mortality distribution

is similar to results of publication from developed and developing countries of the world.⁹

Road traffic-related injuries were the major cause of severe TBI and young men were mostly involved. This finding is similar to that reported by other studies in Nigeria and in other developing countries of the world.^{2,5,8,10} The findings suggest that the incidence of TBI among young adults is on the increase in many developing

countries. This trend could be as a result of increase in urbanization and motorized means of transportation with little observance of traffic regulations.^{10, 11,12,13} Motor vehicular crashes was the most common cause of TBI in this study, reflecting a change in pattern when compared to the study by Solagberu, *et al*,¹⁴ Emejuelu *et al*¹⁵ and Yusuf *et al*⁵ where motorcycle accident was reported to be the most common cause of TBI.

This could be due to the banning and limited use of motorcycle operation within Abuja city centre.

Despite the increasing number of publications on evidence-based guidelines used in the management of patients with TBI in ICU,^{16,21} there is still a wide variation in care processes and outcomes across different trauma centers world over.¹⁷⁻²¹ The mortality rate of 47% obtained in this study is lower than values of 54.8% to 77.3% obtained in other studies in Nigeria. This may be related to the dedicated trauma ICU Model with the use of trained staff on trauma ICU care, capacity for invasive monitoring and the use of Standard Management Protocol (SMP).^{2,5,8} Despite this finding, however, more achievements can be made through strict adherence of SMP, and timely intervention.

Minai *et al*, in a retrospective review at the Aga Khan University Karachi reported a similar finding of 46.1% in a dedicated trauma ICU.¹⁰ This result is approaching the results of publication from developed part of the world with an average mortality of 30%, where standardized management protocols of pre hospital and in-hospital care are being followed. Fakhry and the Brain Trauma Foundation (BTF) proposed a guideline-based management protocol to validate aggressive early interventions.^{22,23} The use of this protocol, results in reduction in mortality from 39% in 1987 to 27% in 1997 as reported by Lu J *et al* and Roukoz *et al*.^{24,25} Cohort 1 reported a mortality of 49.2% among patients with severe TBI with GCS of 3. This study also revealed that good recovery was seen in 23 (26.1%) of the patients who survived and (9%) remained vegetative at discharge.⁸ In this study there was no significant difference in the GOS between male and female patients ($p=0.806$). An average time interval from presentation to ICU admission of 37.98hrs is still high. This may be due to prolonged resuscitation time in the trauma resuscitation unit, this shows a longer time from

presentation to ICU admission when compared to report by Desalu *et al*.² Prompt resuscitation and immediate admission of patient with TBI into the ICU was shown by Baker *et al* to improve survival and mortality.³ Further review of timely intervention and adherence to SMP in the care of TBI patient will be required to further validate the need for a dedicated head trauma critical care unit in Nigeria. Although the result from this study shows an improved outcome in TBI management in a dedicated trauma ICU compared to publications from other parts of Nigeria, there is still the need for a longer duration of study and a comparative cohort in order to validate this finding.

Limitation

This study suggests that the practice of a specialized ICU model has the potential of reducing mortality. However, this study has several limitations that might impact on the interpretation of the data. First, the data was a single, institutional based, retrospectively retrieved data with several incomplete information that limit our analysis. Therefore, the extent to which these data can be generalized to a broader spectrum of trauma ICU care is less clear. Finally, strict adherence to the SMP, the use of ICP monitor and ABG analysis was grossly interfered with due to financial constraints by some of the patients.

Conclusion

Acute severe TBI is responsible for majority of admissions into trauma ICU, and remains the most common cause of Mortality even in dedicated trauma ICU model. An efficient trauma management system with prompt prehospital care, early neuroimaging, timely neurosurgical intervention and subsequent protocol based intensive care management in a properly equipped

dedicated neurosurgical ICU will no doubt improve outcome in our environment.

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Submission Date

30/09/2020

Acceptance Date

28/12/2020

Neurosurgeon and frontline Doctor: Navigating neurosurgical practice during COVID-19 pandemic

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ABSTRACT

Background: The growing population of COVID-19 positive patients worldwide in the face of a relatively static population of health workers including specialist like neurosurgeons means that some of the highly skilled specialists will be recruited as frontline health workers. The objective of this review is to document the experience of a neurosurgeon at the peak of COVID-19 pandemic.

Methods: There was a holding ward for suspected COVID-19 patients and a COVID-19 treatment ward for confirmed COVID-19 positive patients. Only suspected patients had COVID-19 screening. Patients with confirmed COVID-19 infection were scheduled for surgery with full PPEs for the theatre staff but routine patients were scheduled for surgery with hospital staff using KN95 respirator and routine operating gowns. The data of patients who required neurosurgical procedures and presented to our hospital during the lockdown were reviewed.

Results: Nineteen patients presented to the author and required surgical intervention during the lockdown. The mean age was 49 ± 26 years and age ranges were 5 - 85 years. There were 8(42.1%) males and 11(57.9%) females. The most common lesions were brain tumor 10(52.6%). Only one patient had preoperative COVID-19 screening. All patients were managed as per pre-COVID-19 era without delay. There was one mortality due to late presentation.

Conclusion: There is need for neurosurgeons to adopt necessary modifications based on the prevailing circumstances in their respective regions and hospitals to offer their patients the best possible outcome during the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic.

Keywords:

COVID-19, Pandemic, Neurosurgery, Patients, Neurosurgeon, Frontline doctor

Introduction

COVID-19 pandemic is restructuring health care delivery worldwide.^{1,2} The growing population of COVID-19 positive patients worldwide in the face of the relatively static population of health

workers including specialist like neurosurgeons means that some of the highly skilled specialists will be recruited as frontline health workers.^{2,3,4,5} Nigeria has recorded over 50,000 cases and about 1,000 deaths as a result of the pandemic. There

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is worsened pressure on the existing medical facilities and personnel with some specialist hospitals being converted to COVID-19 treatment centers.^{2,6}

Some of the hospitals have to close their doors for their routine patients population to care for the COVID-19 infected individuals while others run both COVID-19 and routine medical services concurrently.⁽⁷⁾ Both hospital types have to recruit their existing personnel including specialists to treat COVID-19 positive patients.⁽⁸⁾ There is a risk of health worker to patient transmission and vice versa but this may be prevented by stringent protocol and appropriate use of PPEs.^{2,8,9,10}

With the growing population of the COVID-19 patients worldwide, most of the health facilities may adopt the protocol of running routine patient services and COVID-19 treatment facility concurrently to cope with and control the pandemic without negative impact on the general patient's population.^{2,5,11} The objective of this review is to document neurosurgical service at the peak of COVID-19 pandemic (Figure 1) in a tertiary hospital where the neurosurgeon is also among the frontline doctors.

Methods

Study design: Retrospective review of the cohort of patients with neurological lesions who presented to the author during COVID-19 pandemic lockdown from April 2020 to July 2020. **Study location:** The hospital is in Suburban community of South West Nigeria with a 300-bed capacity. COVID-19 treatment centre was situated within the hospital by conversion of the existing facility. There was a holding ward for suspected COVID-19 patients and a COVID-19 treatment ward for confirmed COVID-19 positive patients. The hospital has surgical specialties facilities including neurosurgery and the consultant neurosurgeon was also recruited as a frontline doctor to fight COVID-19 pandemic as the only core surgical specialist in the COVID-19 management team. The roles include the

review and coordination of the surgical needs of the suspected and confirmed patients.

The hospital provided routine patients care including clinics, emergencies and surgeries while observing physical distancing, the use of appropriate PPEs for both hospital staff and patients, regular hand washing and the use of alcohol based hand sanitizers during the lockdown in the region. Only suspected patients including patients with a history of travel to Lagos state which is the epicenter in Nigeria had COVID-19 screening.¹² Patients with confirmed COVID-19 infection were scheduled for surgery with full PPEs for the theatre staff. Routine patients were scheduled for surgery with hospital staff using KN95 respirator and routine operating gowns.

The institutional ethical approval was obtained for COVIDSURG study. The data of patients who required neurosurgical procedures and managed to present to our hospital during the lockdown from April 2020 to July 2020 for the first wave of COVID-19 pandemic were reviewed and analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 20. The results were presented using tables. Categorical data were summarized by frequencies, proportions and percentages, while continuous data were summarized using means and standard deviations.

Results

The clinical data of 19 patients who presented to the author with neurosurgical lesions which require surgery during the lockdown were analysed (Table 1). The mean age was 49 ± 26 years and age range was 5 - 85 years. There were 8(42.1%) males and 11(57.9%) females. The most common lesion was brain tumor 10(52.6%) (Table 2). Only one patient had preoperative COVID-19 screening on account of history of contact and she was positive. She was managed at a nearby COVID-19 treatment centre where she had positive COVID-19 screening and referred to our hospital on account of brain MRI confirmed brain tumour.

Table 1.

S/N	Age (Years)	Sex	Diagnosis	Comorbidity	Operation	COVID-19 Infection	Outcome
1	5	F	C _{4,6} bifid spinous processes with fusion of the right half and bony mass	nil	C _{4,6} right hemi-laminectomies excision of bony mass	Not tested	Alive and discharged home
2	7	F	Left CPA tumour with brain stem compression (figure 2)	nil	She had cardiopulmonary arrest after MRI before surgical intervention	Not tested	Dead
3	14	F	Medically resistant seizures secondary to left occipital porencephalus cyst	nil	Left parieto-occipital craniotomy & cystectomy	Not tested	Post-operative satisfactory seizure control.
4	13	F	Diffuse pontine glioma	nil	Referred to another facility for radiotherapy	Not tested	Transferred to other hospital
5	40	M	C ₁ anterior extra-medullary tumour ?meningioma	nil	Awaiting surgery for financial reason	Not tested	Alive
6	47	M	C ₄ non-traumatic myelopathy secondary to cervical spinal canal stenosis	nil	Awaiting surgery for financial reason	Not tested	Alive
7	55	M	Right parietal convexity meningioma (Figure 3)	Hypertension	Craniotomy and gross total tumour excision	Not tested	Alive, no neurological deficit
8	58	M	Tuberculosis of the spine with residual thoracic spinal cord compression	Diabetes and Hypertension	T ₁₀ -T ₁₂ decompressive laminectomies	Not tested	Alive
9	52	F	Right cavernous sinus meningioma	nil	Right tempoparietal craniotomy and near total tumor excision	Not tested	Alive, no neurological deficit

S/N	Age (Years)	Sex	Diagnosis	Comorbidity	Operation	COVID-19 Infection
10	61	F	Right cerebellar convexity extra-axial tumor most likely meningioma	Hypertension	Awaiting surgery for financial reason	Not tested Alive
11	63	F	Lumbar spinal canal stenosis	Diabetes and Hypertension	I ₃ -I ₅ decompressive laminectomy	Not tested Alive, neurogenic claudication improved
12	69	F	Left parieto-occipital glioblastoma	Hypertension	Left parieto-occipital craniotomy and gross total excision	Tested and positive for COVID-19 Post-operative repeat COVID-19 was negative, improving motor gain.
13	70	F	Lumbar spinal canal stenosis	Hypertension	L ₄ -S ₁ decompressive laminectomies	Not tested Alive, neurogenic claudication improved
14	70	M	Cauda equine compression 2 ^o epidural lipomatosis	Hypertension	L ₄ -S ₁ decompressive laminectomy+excision	Not tested Alive, neurogenic claudication resolved
15	72	F	Lumbar spinal canal stenosis	Hypertension	I ₃ -I ₅ decompressive laminectomies	Not tested Alive, neurogenic claudication improved
16	55	M	Recurrent left parietal glioblastoma	Diabetes and Hypertension	Family opted for palliative care	Not tested Discharged home
17	85	F	Left parietal skull tumor? metastasis	nil	Family opted for palliative care	Not tested Alive
18	16	M	Obstructive hydrocephalus secondary to pineal region tumour	nil	Ventriculo-peritoneal shunt	Not tested Parents requested for discharge for definitive surgery when they are financially ready
19	80	M	Butterfly glioblastoma	nil	Family opted for palliative care	Not tested Discharge home

Table 2:
Pattern of neurosurgical lesions

Diagnosis	Sex		Total
	Male	Female	
Congenital spinal lesion	0	1	1
Congenital brain lesion	0	1	1
Brain tumour	4	6	10
Spinal tumour	1	0	1
Tuberculosis of the spine	1	0	1
Degenerative spine disease	2	3	5
Total	8	11	19

Table 3:
Management

	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Surgery as scheduled	11	57.9	57.9
Surgery delayed for financial reason	3	15.8	73.7
Relatives opted for non-operative care	3	15.8	89.5
Referred to another hospital	1	5.3	94.7
Died before surgery	1	5.3	100.0
Total	19	100	

Figure 1. Confirmed COVID-19 Cases - Nigeria 2020 (<https://covid19.ncdc.gov.ng/progression/>)

Accessed on the 13/12/2020

Figure 2a. Brain MRI of a child with left CPA tumour. *The yellow arrow is pointing to the right normal auditory canal, center of green circle is the cone shaped tumour, blue arrow pointing to the displaced fourth ventricle and red arrow pointing to the left vestibular schwannoma compressing the pons*

Figure 2b. Axial T2W MRI, showing relatively preserved lateral ventricle

Figure 3. Brain MRI showing right parietal convexity meningioma with pressure effects

Eleven (57.9%) patients were managed and had their surgeries as per pre-COVID-19 era without delay (Table 3). There was no in-hospital delay due to COVID-19 pandemic. The patient with preoperative COVID-19 infection was treated, became negative post operation and she was discharged home. Operated patients were followed up in clinics. The 30-day post-operative review showed no peri-operative mortality.

There was a late presentation of a patient with left cerebellopontine angle(CPA) tumour with brain stem compression but the ventricles were within normal limits (Figures 2a and 2b). She had cardiopulmonary arrest and died during brain Magnetic Resonant Imaging.

Discussion

The patients' care during COVID-19 pandemic has received global attention with frequent modification of guidelines to prevent exposure to both the uninfected patient and health workers while providing optimal care.^{4, 11} COVID-19 infection like most viral infection is associated with stigmatizations and discriminations and some health facilities closed up in the wake of COVID-19 pandemic while those who open may discriminate against COVID-19 positive or suspected patients.^{13, 14, 15}

Fever and cough are the subjects of suspicion, though it is clear that COVID-19 biology is not fully understood and many patients may present with atypical symptoms.^{7,16} COVID-19 infection is deadly but death from the fear of this infection may be worse and result in increased morbidity and mortality among the un-infected population due to lack of access to prompt and adequate medical attention for medical conditions like complicated obstetric cases, a chronic medical illness like hypertension and diabetes mellitus, and intracranial tumors as one of our patients with CPA tumour.^{6,17,18}

The fear of COVID-19 infection has subjected many patients with acute surgical conditions to delayed surgical intervention and even death.¹⁹ Some neurosurgical patients who appear stable may have lesions with imminent death if surgery is delayed like some patients in this index review (figures 2). Prompt and timely intervention is an essential part of neurosurgical practice for an excellent outcome which may be a challenge during the pandemic.^{3,17}

We provided routine neurosurgical services to our patients who presented during the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown whether elective or emergence cases despite our involvement as frontline doctors. The outcomes were satisfactory and there was no confirmed case of a patient to health worker transmission of COVID-19

infection in our unit. The COVID-19 pandemic has evolved to community transmission and may persist for a longer time.⁸ There is need for health care workers including neurosurgeons who may also be called to join the frontline doctors to embrace this new trend and modify their practice to provide optimal service to routine and COVID-19 positive patients.^{6, 11, 18, 20}

Conclusion

COVID-19 pandemic may persist for a while but we should not allow neurosurgical patients to suffer while we participate in the global response to this deadly virus. There is need for neurosurgeons to adopt necessary modifications and appropriate use of the PPEs based on the prevailing circumstances in their respective regions and hospitals to offer their patients the best possible outcome.

Conflict of interest: The author declared no conflict of interest

Funding: No external funding

Ethical approval: Institutional ethical approval was obtained

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Submission Date

21/11/2020

Acceptance Date

29/12/2020

Cavernous malformation presenting with post-partum intracranial hemorrhage: A case report and review of literature

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ABSTRACT

We report a case of intracranial hemorrhage secondary to ruptured cerebral cavernous malformation (CCM) in a 36-year-old Nigerian female. To our knowledge, this is the first of such report in a Nigerian in the post puerperal period. We highlight its significance as a salient clinical mimic of peripartum eclampsia requiring a heightened clinical acumen. We also reviewed scientific literature relevant to the presentation and management of cryptic vascular malformations presenting with intracranial hemorrhage and discussed the challenges of diagnosis and multidisciplinary care of cryptic cerebral malformations associated with peripartum rupture and intracranial hematoma in our peculiar setting identified with significant resource constraints.

Keywords:

Brain vascular malformation, Eclampsia, Computerized tomographic scan, Magnetic resonance imaging, Craniotomy

Introduction

Brain cavernomas are well established causes of intracranial hemorrhage.^{1,2,3} However, the exact relationship between pregnancy and the puerperium and the risk of clinically significant intracranial hemorrhage from brain cavernomas remains unclear.^{4,5} Although intracerebral hematoma from vascular lesions associated with pregnancy and the post-partum period has a reported incidence of 0.01-0.05 %, ⁶ and accounts

for 5-12% of maternal mortality burden,⁷ the specific contribution of cavernomas is unknown.^{4,8}

Brain hemorrhage from cerebral cavernous malformations (CCM) occurring in association with pregnancy and the puerperium although rare, represents an important differential of eclampsia and therefore offers a significant clinical challenge with respect to diagnosis and management.⁹ This index report is the first to

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describe cavernous malformation in a Nigerian. We believe our report will aid clinicians to heighten their diagnostic suspicion while evaluating patients with similar presentation.

Case Report

A.M. was a 36-year old right-handed multiparous female who presented with severe frontal headache, an episode of left focal seizures and neck pain. She had an emergency caesarean delivery two weeks prior to presentation on account of fetal distress.

There was no preceding history of head trauma. She had history of elevated Blood Pressure -150/90mmHg in the immediate post puerperal period. The main physical findings on presentation were normal vital signs (including a blood pressure of 120/80mmHg), normal mental status, a left incongruous homonymous field defect with bilateral abducens weakness and a left upper motor neuron facioparesis. She had neck stiffness as well as positive Brudzinski's and Kernig's signs. She also had a left upper extremity

Figure 1. Pre-op cranial CT (*non-contrast*) showing right occipital lobe hematoma. Note the hypodense rim (blue arrow) and the hematoma (orange arrow)

Figure 2. Post-op T1WI (A) and T2WI (B) showing site of CCM excision (arrows)

Figure 3. Post-op MRA images showing normal cerebral vasculature

drift and brisk myotatic reflexes. Her urine and blood work up showed normal findings.

Cranial computerized tomographic scan showed a large hyperdense right occipital intracerebral mass with focal subarachnoid hemorrhage (Fig. 1). Cranial CTA showed no vascular lesions. The presence of an acute symptomatic cerebral mass lesion was the main indication for surgery.

A diagnosis of post-partum spontaneous intracerebral hematoma possibly secondary to occult cerebral vascular malformation was made with eclampsia as differential. She had a right occipital craniotomy and evacuation of 100mls of sub-acute right occipital intracerebral blood

clot and microsurgical excisional biopsy of an abnormal friable reddish-brown tissue in the hematoma bed surrounded by a well-defined gliotic capsule. There were no abnormal veins suggestive of a developmental venous anomaly (DVA) within the vicinity of the surgical field. Post-op cranial MRI (Fig. 2), showed neither a residual lesion at the operation site nor similar lesions in other locations.

The histopathological findings were in keeping with cavernous malformation of the right occipital lobe (Fig. 4). Her immediate post op recovery was uneventful. Her visual field defects improved remarkably during follow-up.

Figure 4. Histopathology of biopsy specimen. Abnormal dilated thin walled vascular channels A (white arrow) with absence of intervening neural tissue in A and B (blue arrow) on H/E stain are histopathological features of cavernous malformation

Discussion

Cerebral cavernous malformations also known as cavernomas (CCMs) are intracranial lesions composed of low flow and abnormally dilated capillary endothelial lined channels without intervening neural tissue.^{10,11} Their high permeability predisposes to episodes of focal hemorrhage and thrombosis, resulting in a range of neurological symptoms.¹ In this report, we present a case of intracerebral hemorrhage from cerebral cavernous malformation (CCM) occurring during the post-partum period. Although an autopsy report has described CCMs as common malformations of the systemic and CNS vasculature,^{6, 12} however, clinical studies have reported a range of prevalence between 0.4% to 0.6%.^{1, 12, 13}

The index case, which to our knowledge is the first to be reported in Nigeria, more so, in the post-partum period present us with salient lessons. Firstly, it shows that cavernomas occurs in Nigerians and can pose as eclampsia mimic when resolving the differential diagnosis of spontaneous intracerebral hemorrhage among pregnant women and nursing mothers. Secondly it suggests that pregnancy may alter the natural history of CCM leading to elevated risk of hemorrhage and that this risk alteration may persist even in the puerperium.^{5, 7, 8}

Thirdly it suggests a redefining of the protocol for the diagnostic work-up of pregnant women with symptoms suggestive of eclampsia especially in low and middle income countries to include cranial MRI since cavernomas are angiographically occult and cranial CT Imaging alone may only reveal with certainty, intracranial hemorrhage in CCM patients as was the case in our index report. Previous reports have demonstrated increased hemorrhage rates among females with CCM.^{8, 14}

The higher rates of hemorrhage in females is reinforced by some reports suggesting that CCMs are hormone responsive.^{15, 16, 17} We also believe that elevated levels of maternal hormones during pregnancy and the puerperium may alter

the hemodynamics of the cerebral blood flow sufficiently to provoke rupture of a previously quiescent low flow lesion such as CCM in our patient. We do not know what other factors may influence the timing of the hemorrhage during pregnancy and specifically, the role of fetal distress which was reported in our index case. We hypothesize that causes of fetal distress may be contributory to the state of altered cerebral hemodynamics which provides the substrate for CCM rupture or may in fact be a sequelae of the hematoma. The increased aggressiveness of CCMs in pregnancy has also been previously reported.¹⁸ The finding of subacute hematoma intra-op suggests that the bleed occurred much earlier and perhaps in the early post-delivery period¹⁹ However one previous study has refuted the role of pregnancy in the risk profiling of hemorrhage in CCM.⁴

Although there is no sex predilection judging from an analysis of ten CCM natural history studies,¹⁴ however, female sex has been reported as a risk factor for hemorrhage.^{13, 15} The role of pregnancy and hormonal manipulation on the natural history of CCM will therefore need to be further elucidated. An analysis of the mean age at presentation from previous studies on this subject showed that CCMs are more commonly seen among young adults with an average age of 30.6 years.¹⁴ Our index case was 36 years at presentation and hence falls within this age group. Most CCMs are asymptomatic and angiographically occult.^{2, 11, 20} However common presenting features such as headaches, seizures, and focal neurological deficits place CCMs on the differential horizons of eclampsia which is a more commonly encountered clinical condition among pregnant women.^{14, 20} Our patient had headaches and visual impairment but her normal blood pressure and the absence of protein in her urine suggested other diagnostic possibilities.^{4, 20}

Angiography will usually not demonstrate cavernous malformations, but may show a developmental venous anomaly in the neighborhood of a CCM. Cranial CT scan will

show the hematoma and sometimes suggest the presence of a hypodense (hemosiderin) rim as in our index patient. Cranial MRI will also demonstrate the hematoma and has a higher sensitivity than CT in revealing the hemosiderin rim which is pathognomonic of CCM. Newer acquisitions of MRI such as Fast spin echo (FSE) and currently susceptibility weighted imaging (SWI) are associated with an even higher sensitivity in the diagnosis of CCM and are especially helpful in revealing multiple lesions.²¹ CCM has been classified morphologically by

Zabramski *et al.* based on radiographic appearance and hemorrhage period into four groups.²¹ In the index patient however, the findings on CT were not confirmatory of CCM, hence diagnosis was made intraoperatively and confirmed by histopathological evaluation of the surgical specimen. Cranial MRI was added to our unit's protocol for investigating pregnant women with symptoms suggestive of eclampsia after we successfully managed the index case. Prior to this CT with angiography was the neuroimaging tool in our protocol. We adopted a multidisciplinary approach in the management of the index case and we believe this resulted in an early neurosurgical, neuroradiological, obstetric and anesthetic evaluation and intervention. Craniotomy with total microsurgical excision is the current standard care for symptomatic CCM and this treatment was applied to our index case.

²²Surgery was aided by intraoperative neuroprotection with intravenous agents etomidate, isoflurane and propofol during anaesthesia. These agents have also been previously reported to provide optimal and safe anesthesia during surgery for intracranial vascular malformations.²³ Although the follow-up period can be complicated by re-bleeding from recurrence or the development of de-novo lesions, we followed up the index case for over 5 years with yearly MRI scan. To date, there has been no history of symptom recurrence or new lesion either in the same or other brain locations.²⁴ For patients with known brain cavernous malformations, it

may be advisable to seek genetic counseling before achieving pregnancy especially if there are multiple lesions.²⁵ Brain MRI should be performed if new neurological deficits develop. In patients with uneventful pregnancy and quiescent cavernomas, vaginal delivery is an acceptable mode of birth.²⁵ However, the presence of neurological symptoms or previous history of hemorrhage are considered contraindications to this mode of parturition.²⁵

Conclusion

Intra-cerebral hemorrhage from CCM is a rare but significant differential of eclampsia during pregnancy and the puerperium. It poses both a diagnostic and management challenge which requires a broadened acumen of clinical suspicion as well as timely multidisciplinary intervention. This report concretely describes the occurrence of CCMs in a Nigerian and highlights the need for increased awareness among clinicians of this lesion which perhaps more likely may represent a frequently unrecognized or misdiagnosed presentation rather than a rare clinical conundrum.

Funding

We received no external funding for this work. We do not have any competing interest

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Submission Date

17/07/2020

Acceptance Date

14/10/2020

Cervical myelomeningocele: Our experience with eight cases

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ABSTRACT

Background: Cervical myelomeningocele are rare forms of myelomeningocele with near normal neurologic functions compared to lesions at other levels of the spine. They constitute a peculiar type of myelomeningocele based on their location, morphology and less disabling presentation in most cases.

Objectives: This study examines the characteristics, challenges and outcome of managing cervical myelomeningocele in a regional neurosurgery centre in North-West Nigeria.

Methodology: This is a retrospective study from January 2011 through September 2016 that included patients with cervical myelomeningocele.

Result: Eight (3.3%) out of 243 patients with myelomeningocele had cervical myelomeningocele. The male to female ratio was 5:3. Three patients had ulcerated myelomeningocele and one had right upper extremity monoparesis at presentation.

Conclusion: Cervical myelomeningocele, though rare, are also seen in our subregion. Surgical detethering of the fibroneurovascular band is central to their repair.

Keywords:

Neurulation, Fibroneurovascular stalk, Myelocystocele, Tethered bands, Kinked cord

Introduction

Myelomeningocele result from failure of neural tube closure in the neurulation process¹. Cervical myelomeningocele are rare forms of

myelomeningocele^{2,3}, and account for 1-5% of all neural tube defects^{3,4}.

The concept of neural tube closure has been explained variously by the continuous and

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multisite closure models. In the various described models, the first site of closure is in the future cervical region⁵. Since the neural tube closure progresses in a bidirectional pattern, it begs the question how the other parts the neural tube closes when there is a defect in the first site of closure. This presents the occurrence of cervical myelomeningocele as a paradox of sorts. This conflict is further projected by the absence of the neural placode and the exposed central canal as seen in myelomeningocele at other spine levels.

Patients with cervical myelomeningocele have been known to have near normal neurologic functions than those with the lesion at other levels of the spine³. Published series on the pathology, clinical presentation and surgical management are still limited^{2,3}.

Objective

This study examines the characteristics, challenges and outcome of managing cervical myelomeningocele in a regional neurosurgery centre in North-West Nigeria.

Patients and Methods

This is a retrospective study with information obtained from the case notes of included patients. It covers the period from January 2011 through September 2016. All patients with cervical myelomeningocele were included.

Results

Eight (3.3%) out of 243 patients with myelomeningocele managed during the study period had their lesions in the cervical region. Five of the patients were females (62.5%) and three were males (37.5%) as seen in Figure 2. Seven patients presented at the age of 24 weeks or less while one presented at 4 years of age, with the mean age of presentation being 34.36 weeks.

Six of the patients were products of unbooked pregnancies and six patients had

CERVICAL MYELOMENINGOCELE

Figure 1. A baby with cervical myelomeningocele

spontaneous vaginal delivery with no indication of periconceptional folic acid use. Three patients had ulcerated myelomeningocele and one had right upper extremity monoparesis at presentation (Table 1).

All the patients had surgical intervention and the intraoperative findings include: tethering bands in 2 cases, herniating spinal cord in one, lipomatous tissue attached to dura in one, meningocele in three patients and kinked spinal cord in the patient who died post-operatively (Table 2).

Two patients had post-operative complications of which one had partial wound dehiscence and the other, who was lost to follow up, had pseudomeningocele. The mortality recorded was caused by post-operative aspiration pneumonitis with suspected ascending cord oedema.

The shortest interval between presentation and surgery was 4 days and longest interval was 155 days. The reasons for delayed surgical treatment included lack of bedspace and subsequent optimisation for surgery in one, parents' default from clinic visits, upper respiratory tract infection in one and ulcerated myelomeningocele in three cases.

The longest duration of follow up was for 251 days after discharge and four patients never presented for follow up. One patient was advised

Table 1:
Clinical summaries of eight patients

S/N	Age(Wks) /Sex	Pre-OP Deficit	Ulcerated	Booked	Mode of Delivery*	Place of Delivery*	Folic Acid Use	Intra-Operative Findings
P1	24/M	Nil	Yes	No	SVD	Home	Nil	Meningocele
P2	2/F	Nil	No	No	SVD	Home	Nil	Tethering bands
P3	5/M	Nil	Yes	No	SVD	Home	Nil	Meningocele
P4	3/M	Nil	Yes	No	SVD	Home	Nil	Meningocele
P5	6/F	Nil	Nil	Yes	SVD	Hospital	N/A	Herniated cord
P6	8/F	Right upper extremity monoparesis	Nil	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Lipomatous tissue/tethering
P7	208(4yrs) /F	Nil	Nil	No	SVD	Home	N/A	Tethering band
P8	12/F	Nil	N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	Kinked cord

*SVD- Spontaneous vaginal delivery.

Figure 2.

Table 1:
Clinical summaries of eight patients

S/N	Intra-Operative Findings
P1	Meningocele
P2	Tethered bands
P3	Meningocele
P4	Meningocele
P5	Herniating cervical spinal cord
P6	Lipomatous tissue attached to the dura
P7	Tethered bands
P8	Kinked spinal cord

to continue follow up at a peripheral hospital due to distance.

Discussion

Cervical myelomeningocele are rare congenital lesions^{2,6}. They account for 1-5% of all neural tube defects^{3,4}. Our series of 8(3.3%) out of 243 cases of myelomeningocele conform with cited reports. The diagnosis of cervical meningocele

and myelomeningocele are obvious at birth⁶, and most studies, like our series, found a female preponderance³.

Controversy abound regarding the classifications of cystic cervical lesions which are regarded as myelomeningoceles because they all contain nervous tissue. One of such classifications divides the lesions into two subgroups of fibroneurovascular stalk and myelocystocele. The subgroup with fibroneurovascular stalk has a stalk containing neurons, glia and peripheral nerves inside a dural sac, while myelocystocele is defined as a central sac of glia or neural tissue within a meningocele. Histologically, meningoceles contain bands of fibrous tissues or neuroglial cells³.

Though we reported three cases with meningoceles as intra operative findings, they were not subjected to histologic examination to confirm or rule out the presence of neural or glia tissue in the sac excised.

The embryologic origin of cervical myelomeningocele is uncertain as most of the neurulation process presumably occurs normally except for the final fusion of apposed neural fold; the basic architecture of the neural tube has also been achieved, except for a thin slip in the dorsal midline. At this point, separation between cutaneous ectoderm and neuroectoderm is never completed. It is noted, however, that the midline gap between the converging cutaneous ectoderm and the dorsal scleromyotomes from opposite sides of the embryo remains narrow³.

Most patients with cervical myelomeningoceles, as we found in our series, have no neurologic deficit^{3,6}. Progressive neurological deterioration is however noted in untreated tethered cervical spinal cord⁶. Hydrocephalus has been reported in 39-50% of cases, and, while Chiari II malformation is less common compared myelomeningoceles in other spine levels, it is more common in the myelocystocele subgroup. Functional disorders such as bladder dysfunction or mirror movement confirms minor prenatal spinal cord dysplasia³.

Intraoperative dura exploration and detethering is essential alongside repair. Neurologic deterioration has been documented in cases without detethering³. In addition, associated anomalies may vary the extent of surgical repair. Patients with associated diastematomyelia in certain series may require repair at the same sitting².

Conclusion

Cervical myelomeningocele, though rare, is also seen in our subregion. Most of the patients were products of unbooked pregnancies and all had vaginal delivery at home except one. Surgical repair with detethering of fibroneurovascular bands is central to treatment. Awareness is needed to improve antenatal bookings and periconceptional folic acid use.

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Submission Date

18/10/2020

Acceptance Date

13/12/2020

Playing wind instruments as a risk factor for chronic subdural haematoma: A report of two cases

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ABSTRACT

Chronic Subdural Haematoma is a common neurosurgical disorder often requiring surgical intervention. The incidence increases with age but can occur in the young. In the young, no known aetiological risk factor may be present. We present two patients managed for chronic subdural haematoma, one a teenager, the other an elderly man with no apparent aetiological factor other than playing of wind instruments. From mounting evidence in the literature regarding the Valsalva effect produced by wind instruments and previous reports linking them to chronic subdural haematoma, we opined that history of playing wind instrument should be explored in patients with this condition especially when no other risk factor is identified.

Key words:

Wind instruments, Valsalva effect, Risk factor, Young, Elderly

Introduction

Chronic Subdural Haematoma (CSDH) is a common cause for neurosurgical consultation, comprising 22% of indications for neurosurgical intervention in adults in a study in Ethiopia.¹ Since it was first described by Virchow as “pachymeningitis haemorrhagic interna”, the condition has long been associated with aging even though it does occur in young patients.^{2,3} Rahme *et al.* in 1961 first drew the attention of the medical

community to the not so infrequent occurrence of CSDH in the young when he reported 19% of his series of 80 patients to be aged 5 years to 40 years.⁴ While head injury, falls, use of anticoagulants and antiplatelets on a background of senile atrophy of the brain are the most widely recognized risk factors in the elderly population, the younger patients share some risk factors with some peculiarities.^{3,5-7} Playing of wind instruments such as the flute, trumpet and saxophones has

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been reported in few publications as a risk factor for CSDH.^{8,9} Much attention, however, has not been given to this Valsalva effect cause that can affect the profession or hobby of many individuals worldwide. We report two cases of CSDH to highlight the potential risk of playing wind instruments as a risk factor in both the young and the elderly.

Case Reports

Case 1

A 14-year-old student presented to our clinic with headache of three weeks and three episodes of vomiting. He had no history of loss of consciousness, memory impairment, seizures or

personal sessions at home during the week. He was conscious and alert with normal findings on neurologic examination. A diagnosis of raised intracranial pressure from a possible intracranial space occupying lesion was made. He subsequently had a magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) done which revealed a left sided chronic subdural haematoma with ipsilateral ventricular effacement and midline shift (Figure 1a).

Complete blood count and clotting profile were normal. An assay of clotting factors could however not be performed. He had burr hole drainage of 'motor oil' subdural collection which was under pressure. The symptoms resolved and he was discharged home post-operative day 2.

Figure 1. Preoperative T2W MRI of 14 years old male with multiloculated left frontoparietotemporal hyperintense collections in the subdural space with mass effect

Figure 1: (a) Preoperative T2W MRI of 14 years old male with multiloculated left frontoparietotemporal hyperintense collections in the subdural space with mass effect (b) Contrast CT scan of same patient done 30 days post burr hole drainage of CSDH showing hypodense lesions in the left frontoparietal and temporal subdural space. (c) Intraoperative images showing (a) multi-layered subdural collection (d) cortical surface with normal vessels post evacuation of collection

focal neurologic deficit. There was no history of involvement in contact sport or trauma to the head. He had no background morbidity and was not on any medications and had no history of drug abuse, alcohol intake or smoking. He was a member of his church choir and played the trumpet every weekend as well as during periodic

He however re-presented within a month with recurrence of headache and an episode of right sided focal tonic-clonic seizures. He had a brain computerized tomography (CT) scan which revealed a reaccumulation of the subdural collection with mass effect (Figure 1b) for which he subsequently had craniotomy and drainage.

Figure 2: Contrast CT scan of same patient done 30 days post burr hole drainage of CSDH showing hypodense crescentic lesions in the left frontoparietal and temporal subdural space.

Figure 3. Intraoperative images showing (a) multi-layered subdural collection (b) inner membrane (c) and cortical surface with normal vessels post evacuation of collection

Intraoperative findings showed multi-loculated subdural collections with thick membranes (Figure 1c&d). No cortical vessel malformation was noticed intraoperatively. He had an uneventful

recovery and was discharged home on post-operative day 5. He has been followed up in clinic with no recurrence in 18 months. He has since switched to playing the guitar and piano.

Case 2

An 86-year-old professional musician presented at the emergency room with a week history of inability to move the left upper and lower limbs and a three-day history of loss of consciousness. He had no history of trauma to the head or fall. He was a known hypertensive controlled on medication, but no history of the use of anticoagulants or antiplatelets. He was still active

Discussion

Chronic subdural haematoma is a common neurosurgical entity with various theories on its pathogenesis. There is no controversy as to what constitute risk factors for this condition. Among the risk factors are aging with associated cerebral atrophy, trauma (many times mild or unnoticed) to the head, anticoagulant and antiplatelet use, alcoholism, ventriculoperitoneal shunting and

Figure 4. Cranial CT scan of 86 years old male with (a) right frontoparietal acute on chronic subdural haematoma (b). Post craniotomy scan with acute subdural haematoma

A

B

in playing musical instruments, particularly saxophone which he taught every weekend. A diagnosis of ischaemic stroke was made at a peripheral hospital until a computerized tomography scan of the brain revealed a right sided chronic subdural haematoma (Figure IIa) which prompted his referral. He had craniotomy for evacuation of the subdural collection. He deteriorated two days later and a repeat CT scan showed an acute subdural haematoma (Figure IIb) that was subsequently evacuated. He was discharged home after two weeks on admission. He has been followed up for three years with no clinical recurrence recorded.

seizure disorders.⁷ The diagnosis of CSDH in the elderly can be obvious. In the young, however, it can easily be missed on clinical ground.¹⁰ This is particularly so when no history of common risk factors is present. The clinical features in our first case raised the suspicion of an intracranial space occupying lesion with CSDH not even a differential until imaging was done. Although many series on CSDH report that it is a rare entity in ages less than 40 years, some studies have revealed that 6.3% -25% of CSDHs occurred in children and young adult.¹⁰⁻¹² A review of our unpublished series revealed that 10% of our patients with CSDH are aged less than 50 years.

A history of trauma to the head or fall is often present in CSDH but was absent in our patients. While a remote or trivial fall that patient may have not reckoned with is not impossible in the second patient, it seems unlikely in the first case. Liliang et al. in their study revealed that time from trauma to presentation is usually short in younger patients with a mean of 31.5 days compared to 50.3 days in elderly.¹³ As such, one will expect them to recollect the history of trauma which is also usually more significant in them than in the elderly. Some authors have alluded to the fact that falls may actually not precede CSDH but rather, the presence of the haematoma itself and its effects may have predisposed patients to fall. This is supported by the fact that some patients with CSDH with a shorter duration of fall prior to presentation have been documented to have older haematomas on CT scan.¹²

Although the coagulation studies and platelet counts were normal in our patients, they cannot completely rule out bleeding tendencies as clotting factor deficiencies could not be ruled out in them. Dorban et al. advocated that the possibility of clotting factor deficiency should be considered in patients younger than sixty years.¹⁴ They found seven of their 16 patients younger than 60 years with spontaneous CSDH had deficiencies of factor VII and von Willibrand factor, although the tests were performed post treatment.

A number of peculiar risk factors have been reported for spontaneous CSDH in children.¹⁵ The playing of a wind instrument was the only risk factor we could elicit in the 14-year-old male. Valsalva manoeuvres reduce venous return from the brain causing venous congestion and momentarily raise the intracranial pressure. They have been shown to cause an increase in intracranial pressure by up to 100% of base line.¹⁶ The process of playing wind instruments create a Valsalva effect and over time, rupture of small vessels may occur and lead to gradual accumulation of blood in the subdural space. Wang et al. were the first to report this mechanism

as a cause of CSDH in a 14-year old flute player.⁸ Brenna *et al.* had earlier reported same in a 37 year old saxophonist.⁹ The effects of other risk factors such as dehydration associated with running, marathon, frequent use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs may have played some role in his patient. There are publications that have also linked the Valsalva effects of playing wind instruments to pressure related nervous system diseases. Martinez-Lage et al. reported two 10-year-old males, one with Chiari malformation and the other with obstructive hydrocephalus that had headaches aggravated by playing wind instruments.¹⁷ Symptoms decreased in the Chiari malformation patient with decreased playing of the wind instrument while the hydrocephalic patient was treated with endoscopic third ventriculostomy. Similarly, significant rise in intraocular pressure has also been documented during blowing of wind instruments.⁵

Conclusion

We advocate that clinicians should make attempts to elicit possibility of Valsalva manoeuvre such as playing wind instruments as being a risk or an aggravating factor in patients with chronic subdural haematoma particularly in young patients with no other risk factor. The consideration of this may play a role in counselling patients to avoid recurrence.

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Submission Date

16/07/2020

Acceptance Date

14/10/2020

Ultrasound guided extraction of intracranial bullet, an option in a resource poor setting

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Craniocerebral gunshot injuries are emerging epidemics in Sub-Sahara Africa due to political unrest. There is a need for a robust neurosurgical protocol for managing patients. Metallic components of impaled bullets are injurious to the brain, and should be removed where feasible. Image guided extraction of the bullet reduces iatrogenic injury. Stereotaxy, intraoperative MRI, and C-arm are often non-existent in resource poor settings. Ultrasound is an alternative, though less favoured. It is readily available and users friendly.

Case Description: A 24 year old boy with deep seated right temporal bullet sustained from a stray bullet. He had right temporal craniectomy, ultrasound scan was used to localize the bullet, then durotomy plus gyrotomy was done leading to the extraction of the bullet located deep in the right temporal lobe.

Conclusion: Ultrasound guidance is a viable option in the extraction of intracranial bullet in resource poor settings.

Keywords:

Ultrasound- guided extraction intracranial bullet, Option resource poor setting

Introduction

Craniocerebral gunshot injuries are emerging epidemics. The political unrest with the attendant unfortunate arms proliferation in most developing countries may account for these. Nigeria and Sub-Sahara African countries have had their fair share

of the civil unrest. Robust neurosurgical protocol is often necessary for optimum care of patients with craniocerebral gunshot injuries. Adequate care will reduce the risk of infection and the theoretical risk of seizure. Metallic components of the bullets are also injurious to the brain

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substance overtime. ¹ Hence, surgical removal of pellets and bullets is the goal where this is attainable. This should however not be at the detriment of neurological function. Radiological localization obviously will reduce tissue injury in an attempt to remove an intracranial foreign body thereby reducing the postoperative neurological deficit.^{2,3} Stereotaxy and C-arm machines are not readily available in resource poor settings. The role of ultrasonography in the extraction of intracranial foreign bodies has been reported.⁴ Ultrasound is readily available and does not require so much technicalities during usage. We present our experience with the use of ultrasound in the extraction of a bullet that was lodged in the right temporal lobe.

Case summary

A 23-year old right handed male student who hails and resides in Nnewi, South-East Nigeria. He presented with transient loss of consciousness of five days duration following a gunshot injury. He was in apparent steady state of health until five days before presentation when while in front of his house he sustained a scalp injury from a stray bullet which bled profusely. He also lost consciousness immediately but recovered from it shortly. There were facial twitches which lasted few seconds and resolved spontaneously. In

Figure1. Clinical picture
The entry point is shown with a blue arrow

Figure 2. Cranial CT
Shows calvarial defect (star) and bullet in right temporal region (blue arrow)

addition, he had left hemibody weakness which was persistent. There was no craniofacial efflux nor other collateral injury. He was initially taken to a prayer house before being taken to a hospital where initial resuscitation was done.

At presentation, he was not in any obvious distress. There was no sign of chronic systemic illness.

Respiratory rate was 20 counts per minute, pulse rate 60 beats per minute, blood pressure 110/70 mmHg, temperature was 37 degrees Celsius.

Glasgow coma score was 15, while the high cerebral functions were intact.

Pupils were 3mm bilaterally and briskly reactive to light. There was left facioparesis (LMN type) as well as left upper extremity monoparesis: wrist extension and flexion were 2/5, others were 5/5. There was punctate healing wound on the right parietal entry wound (figure 1). Other neurologic and systemic examination findings were unremarkable.

Cranial CT scan showed right temporal intraparenchymal bullet, and right parietal

Figure 3. Scout film
Shows the bullet (red arrow)

Figure 4. Axial cranial CT
Shows trajectory of the bullet (red arrow)

depressed calvarial fracture. There was also a right parietal contusion (figures 2,3, 4).

He was worked up for wound debridement, elevation of depressed skull fracture and ultrasound guided extraction of temporal intraparenchymal impaled bullet.

Operation details

This was done under general anaesthesia with endotracheal intubation after obtaining an informed consent, a right temporal incision was made just above the level of the external auditory meatus after calculating the locus with the CT scan that was available. A temporal burrhole was made and extended into a minicraniotomy to provide window for the ultrasound probe. Durotomy was also done and attempt was then made to localize the bullet with the ultrasound probe while Watson Chyne was used to sound the located bullet. In the process, a brain swelling was encountered. This was initially managed with hyperventilation and mannitol infusion. This was however unsuccessful necessitating a decision to do a hemicraniotomy (osteoplastic bone flap fig 4) and durotomy to give room for adequate brain relaxation. This was via a wide question mark incision with an anteriorly based scalp flap. The ultrasound was again deployed to localize the bullet (see attached video). Middle temporal gyrotomy was done and the bullet was localized, palpated and extracted with Allis forcep (figures 5, 6 and 7). Haemostasis was secured and the corticotomy created was lined with oxidized cellulose. Augmented pericranial and temporalis

Figure 5. Intraoperative picture
Showing a hemicranial defect

Figure 6. Clinical picture
Showing the bullet picked up with an Allis forcep

Figure 7. Clinical picture
Shows the extracted bullet

fascial duroplasty was done and the osteoplastic flap was replaced and tagged at the base bilaterally. The wound was closed in layers. Sterile wound dressing was applied.

Discussion

Bullets usually are made from a variety of substances including copper, zinc, lead, steel, polymers, rubber and even wax^{5,6,7} Some of these substances, especially lead, are injurious to the brain substance. Some of the documented mechanism for lead toxicity include oxidative stress, altered membrane biophysics, deregulation of cell signaling and impairment of neuronal transmission.⁷ Astrocytes are parts of targets for lead toxicity with attendant glial cell deaths. Lead has also been associated with brain damage and adverse effect on cognitive development.^{8,9} Copper has also be shown to be toxic to the brain parenchymal.

The effect of belated migration of bullet in the brain has also been documented.¹⁰ This could adversely affect the brain. Besides, intracranial bullet is a foreign substance which can also be a seizure and infective foci.¹¹ Hence, the outright removal of bullet lodged in the brain should be the first consideration where this could be achieved. The risk of surgical excision of bullet however must be weighed against neurological deterioration from iatrogenic neurological injury.

Option of image guided procedure reduces the risk of further injury to the already damaged brain. It is minimally invasive. Different intraoperative imaging methods are available for accurate localization of intraparenchymal lesions. When this is combined with good anatomic consideration, risk of further neurologic damage could be reduced.

In the review of image guided surgery in the management of craniocerebral gunshot injuries, 28 patients were prospectively reviewed. The use of stereotaxy, C-arm guidance and free-hand-based surgery were compared. Elser et. al were able to confirm that the eventual functional outcome was better with image assistance (stereotaxy or C-arm guidance).¹²

In resource poor setting as seen in most developing countries, availability of stereotaxy,

intraoperative MRI or CT, even C arm for surgery could be a tall order. Ultrasound has been available for decades during which it is used as a part of diagnostic armamentarium. It has however continued to make an increasing inroads into the operating room. Ultrasound machine is cheap and available. It could be easily deployed for intraoperative localization. The different sizes of the probe could help in the optimal localization. Though effectiveness of intraoperative ultrasound could be improved with other modalities like neuro-navigation where it is available.¹³

Generally, the craniectomy defect created makes the conduction of the piezoelectric transducer feasible hence transmission of the ultrasonic waves generated. These waves are emitted with distinct emission frequencies at the surface of the transducer that is placed on the region of the brain of interest while the returning echoes are subsequently detected by the applicator and processed to visual analogues which are then displayed on monitor screen.¹⁴ Ultrasound has been used by different workers in localizing intracranial lesion intraoperatively^{15,16,17,18} Intraoperative ultrasound is devoid of intricate technicalities, hence it is user friendly. Real-time ultrasound can be used to guide instrument intraoperatively thereby making removal of bone fragments and foreign body possible.¹⁹ It is also not capital intensive and does not depend on radiations unlike fluoroscopy. Intraoperative ultrasound has however been noted to be less precise than intraoperative MRI.¹⁷ Its real time use during surgery makes the problem of 'brain shift' after durotomy reasonably ameliorated.

Funding

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

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Submission Date

16/08/2020

Acceptance Date

14/10/2020

Charting a course for outpatient telemedicine in surgical neurooncology in a Sub-Saharan African setting with a leverage on the Covid-19 pandemic: A pilot study

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ABSTRACT

Background: The patients with brain tumors in the LIMCs are faced with challenges, varying from deficits in neurosurgical manpower, low/absent health insurance coverage, and inadequate healthcare infrastructure. The Covid-19 pandemic has further impacted the care of these patients due to lockdown measures, closure of outpatient clinics and suspension of routine operating schedules. We report our experience, in studying the feasibility and acceptability of outpatient telemedicine in surgical neurooncology patients, which to the best of our knowledge, is the first from Sub-Saharan Africa.

Methods: Brain tumor patients from our departmental database were recruited. Instructions regarding videoconferencing consultations were discussed with them and their caregivers. A commercial videoconferencing platform, Zoom, was used. A questionnaire was administered afterwards to the patients for their evaluation of the process. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze our findings.

Result: Twenty consultations were held for 19 patients; 7 males and 12 females. 8 were post-operative patients. The age range was 15years-84years. The mean consultation time was 30minutes with a range of 20-45 minutes. Imaging was requested in five of the patients due to new symptoms, or for follow up. All the patients were comfortable with the consultation, which they perceived to be helpful, time and cost saving. The average data cost was 1000Naira (\$3) compared to the average cost for clinic attendance 12000Naira (\$30). 36% of the patients will opt for telemedicine consultation in lieu of physical clinic consultation.

Conclusion: Outpatient telemedicine for surgical neurooncology in Sub-Saharan Africa is feasible, cost effective and acceptable. This possibility should be explored to improve patient care.

Keywords:

Telemedicine, Surgical Neurooncology, Sub-Saharan Africa, Covid-19

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Introduction

The declaration of the Coronavirus as a pandemic by the WHO in March 2020, and Nigeria having recorded her first case on the February 27th, 2020 prompted a flurry of activities both nationally and across all the states in Nigeria¹⁴. The country was placed on near complete lock down, with complete ban on inter-state travels and varying levels of ban on intra-city activities. As a precautionary measure in curtailing the spread of the virus, protecting patients and healthcare staff and making provisions for the availability of a fragile health system that has very little capacity for additional level of stress, most government hospitals cancelled routine clinics and restricted surgical services mainly to life or limb threatening emergencies¹⁸. The Neurosurgical service was one of the most hit as a significant number of our patients required post-operative ICU care. The country has since continued to record increasing number of COVID-19 cases, within the milieu of the limited testing capacity, though mortality has remained at about 2.9% of the diagnosed cases as at June 8, 2020.

Thus, our concern was shifted to the challenge of providing care for the neurooncology patients, who prior to this time were usually faced with a myriad of problems, which includes low coverage of the national health insurance scheme, resulting in mostly out of pocket treatment payment, intercity travels mainly by roads, late diagnosis with the resultant large tumor burden associated with operative morbidity and mortality and the challenge of availability of adjuvant therapies such as chemotherapy and radiotherapy^{4, 10}.

Prior to the Covid-19 pandemic, there were only a handful of reports of the use of telemedicine in neurosurgery including the neurooncology specialty and it was mainly for outpatients follow up of patients^{7, 8, 17, 21}. However, with the resultant shelter in place measures aimed to flatten the curve of the COVID-19 infection, there has been an increase in the use of telemedicine in surgical neurooncology units^{9, 12}. Whilst various methods including e-mails,

WhatsApp messages, SMS and particularly telephone calls have been reported in maternal and child health issues, as well as in breast cancer patients in Nigeria^{6, 13, 19}, there has not been any report on the use of virtual video conferencing type of telemedicine in Nigeria, especially in the areas of oncology care and neurooncology in particular. A reluctance to adopt telemedicine has been reported amongst a cohort of Nigerian physicians, mainly attributed to the perception of it constituting dual responsibility for the patients that is not remunerated¹. The lack of infrastructure can also be regarded as a critical factor.

The Covid-19 pandemic led to the increasing use of a number of commercial videoconferencing platforms, across a number of sectors, for meetings and educational activities due to the shelter in measures. We therefore decided to utilize one of these platforms to test the feasibility of utilizing telemedicine outpatient surgical neurooncology consultation and document its acceptability to our patients. This is an account of our experience, which is to the best of our knowledge, the first from Sub-Saharan Africa.

Methodology

The University College Hospital, Ibadan, is a 900-bedded hospital, located in Ibadan, a city with a population of over 3-million people. The hospital serves as the main neurosurgical referral center, for not just the southwestern part of the country but the whole country as a whole, particularly for brain and spinal cord tumors due to the availability of multi-disciplinary expertise.

We searched our database to identify brain tumor patients who were due for routine clinic visits, and also included four new consults. The second author, AB, a resident staff, did the pre-scheduling and scheduling activity, since there was no prior established telemedicine arrangement for reaching these patients. This was carried out between the months of April and June

2020. Twenty-one patients were reached by phone with 19 agreeing to participate. The two that declined did so mainly on the basis of non-compatible phones. The patients were a mix of pre-operative and post-operative patients. The 19 participating patients were instructed to download the Zoom app (which was the commercial videoconferencing platform we utilized) on their smartphones/tablets/laptops. Thus, they did not incur any new cost in getting the gadgets. They were instructed on the functioning of the app with particular mention on the need to reduce background noise, ensure adequate room lighting, and the need for privacy to allow for some basic clinical examination^{9, 15}. Preferred caregivers, family members or relatives were welcomed to be a part of the consultation.

The surgical team reviewed the patient's clinical notes as available and complimented by the team's previous interactions with the patient and images prior to the consultation.

At the pre-arranged time, virtual connection was effected with the patient and rapport established over the first few minutes. This allowed the patient to get adapted to this new modality of consultation. Review of the patient's clinical status was then done, with review of images as necessary through screen sharing via the zoom application. New symptoms and concerns were noted.

Examination during the session included evaluation of the level of consciousness, speech, memory, concentration, gait, ocular movement, facial symmetry, gross motor strength with demonstration of the pronator drift and shoulder shrug. We were also able to examine the wound in a recently operated patient.

We subsequently requested participants to report their experiences through a post telemedicine questionnaire shown in Table 1. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics.

Results

Twenty real time videoconferencing consultations were held, with a patient having two

consultations; a follow up to review the requested brain imaging. There were four new consults, while the rest were either pre-operative patients previously reviewed in the routine clinic or post-operative patients.

The mean videoconferencing consultation time was 30-minutes with a range of 20-45 minutes. There were 7 males and 12 female patients. Their age range was 15years-84years. The virtual consultation resulted in the request for brain imaging in five of the patients either due to development of new symptoms, or as a follow up imaging. Medications were also reviewed.

All the patients completed the questionnaire and reported finding the app easy to download. 84% of the patients reported the Internet connection as good/very good. One of the consultations could not be concluded as planned due to poor cell phone reception. All the patients reported being comfortable during the consultation, had no concerns about privacy and found the interaction helpful. The least rating was 7/10 for the consultation. About 36% of the patients (mainly the post-op patients) will rather have the telemedicine consultation in lieu of physical clinic consultation, while the rest thought it should complement their routine clinic visits. All the patients affirmed that the virtual consultation was cost saving: the average data cost was 1000Naira (about \$3) compared to the average transportation cost for clinic attendance 12000Naira (\$30) and this ranged from 1500-60000 Naira (\$4-\$158). They also alluded to a significant reduction in the stress of attending the physical clinic, considering that the distance from the patients abode to the hospital varied from 5km-726km. However, almost 50% of the patients thought that the lack of physical interaction may pose a challenge in the future.

Discussion

The measures put in place to check the spread of the covid-19 infection since its outbreak, has impacted on the provision of routine care for all patients. Specifically, there has been a challenge

Table 1:

Summary of survey questions

Questions	Yes	No
Was the app easy to download	100%	0%
Were you and your caregiver comfortable	100%	0%
Was the Consultation helpful	100%	0%
Do you think this is cost saving	100%	0%
Was the consultation time saving	100%	0%
Would you prefer Telemedicine to routine clinic attendance	36%	64%
Were your concerns adequately addressed	100%	0%
Any Privacy Concerns	0%	100%
Surgical Status	Preop – 11 (58%)	Post-op – 8 (42%)
Challenges envisaged in the future	Lack of physical contact – 57%	Internet network Concerns-37%

to patient care posed by the lockdown measures, with a ban on inter-state travels, coupled with the closure of outpatient clinics and a stoppage of routine operating sessions. This has placed the oncologic patients, particularly patients with neurooncology diseases, at an increased risk of delayed presentation to the specialists with the resultant possible attendant morbidities and anxiety for both the patients and caregivers. This is also in the context of the fact that the patients with brain and spinal cord tumors are also more vulnerable to the COVID-19 infection particularly during adjuvant treatment with chemotherapy and radiotherapy, which further challenges their immunity.

It was therefore pertinent to seek a balance between the continuing access and provision of care to reducing the risk of exposure of these patients to the Covid-19 disease. This posed a challenge within our setting, as in other LMIC countries, where the utilization of formal telemedicine within the healthcare system is either absent or low, due to a lack of commitment to pursuing the technological investment involved in such. The level of poverty impacting on the ability to afford appropriate Internet access and telephony technology will also be an important

contributor³. To explore the possibility of providing telemedicine care for our neurooncology patients in our public hospital, we leveraged on the increasing access to the Internet by the telecom providers and the decreasing cost of such access, as well as the fact that a significant number of Nigerians are said to either own or have a relative that owns a smart phone, as reported in a cohort of study participants in Lagos, Nigeria².

We found most patients that we contacted excited to participate, even though it was a process they were unfamiliar with. They made efforts in conjunction with their caregivers to have the requirements for a smooth consultation to take place. Caregivers present during the consultations helped with some aspects of the examinations. We had a close relative of one of the patients joined in from another country, thereby providing an avenue for relatives, irrespective of geographical distances, to partake in the care of the patients. This is also often important in our clime, as the funding of the care of the patient is usually a shared responsibility within the family. Though nervousness and a reluctance to want to communicate with the physicians using video based systems have been reported amongst

oncology patients¹¹, our patient's reported being comfortable, having no privacy issues, and finding the interactions meaningful. These findings tally with those of previous reports^{7,16}. The virtual consultations resulted in significant reduction in the cost and stress of travels, supporting previously established evidence^{20, 23}. This importantly removed the burden of routine, or follow up clinic visits for these patients, considering the fact that most of the patients have to fund their healthcare from 'out-of-pocket'. Utilization of virtual consultation Post Covid-19, will also impact on the possible blunting of man-hour loss with resultant income loss¹⁷ and fatigue by caregivers. This has the import of reducing financial losses incurred by the families, from the treatment of these patients and perhaps reducing diagnosis-treatment interval, which is impacted by the ability to fund the cost of surgery. That only 36% of the patients will prefer Telemedicine consultation in the future is a reflection of the predominance of pre-operative patients in our study as opposed to the finding in another study¹⁷. This also explains the concerns of 57% of the patients regarding physical contact with the physician, but more importantly, it points to the fact that telemedicine can be tailored to the needs and desire of the patients per time, and is a reasonable diagnostic and screening platform of pre-operative patients/new consults and for the follow up of post-operative patients^{7,21}. Overall, this seems to have the potential of improving patient's care by replacing or complimenting the routine physical clinics.

The video teleconferencing allowed for the basic examination of the brain tumor patients, and facilitated appropriate decision^{5,9} though we acknowledge our inability to perform examinations requiring detailed strength, sensory, reflex and every one of the cranial nerve examinations¹⁷. It also provided the possibility of having video-conferencing with other physicians caring for the patients such as neurologists, endocrinologists etc., and also open up the possibility of tumor board teleconferencing

within a single institution or across multiple institutions.

While we acknowledge the possible advantages of telemedicine in the care of surgical neurooncology patients in our settings, we do recognize some of the challenges, which include the burden of scheduling, non-recognition of this as an essential part of clinical service for the physician, dual internet funding for both patients and the managing team, internet access with appropriate bandwidth, and phone compatibility. The latter two points are particularly germane in the rural and poor areas. It is therefore imperative that the hospital authorities and departments invest in the basic minimum requirement and bear the burden of the cost, thereby taking the burden off the physicians. Although some of the commercial platforms were previously deemed secured, there were some concerns during the Covid-19 crises, following reports of intrusion from unwanted hackers, likely due to the increase volume in usage. The issue of confidentiality can be addressed by the adherence to basic medical ethics, by the team and also reducing access to any saved data²². The use of the platform may also be an increased burden on a single surgeon, in a large practice, especially after the Covid-19 crises. Therefore, having to prioritize patients from long distances may be helpful in this regard.

Conclusion

The Covid-19 pandemic has opened a new vista with respect to the possibility of telemedicine surgical neurooncology care in low resource areas and it appears that this is feasible, acceptable and convenient to the patients, cost-effective, safe and satisfying for the physicians. We think the myriad of challenges that have hitherto bedeviled this possibility can be more readily surmounted going forward.

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Submission Date

02/11/2020

Acceptance Date

29/12/2020

Neurosurgeon and frontline Doctors: Navigating neurosurgical practice during COVID-19 Pandemic

The issue of Covid-19 infection and the risk posed to neurosurgeons is important and topical. It is highly relevant and calls for each facility to decide on the most appropriate procedures and processes. There is no one size fits all approach and flexibility is important.

The patient characteristics requires clear definition. Who is the patient and their neurological problem that requires solution? Can it wait or be managed conservatively till after this crisis is over? Finally, what is their Covid-19 status (negative or positive) if we must interact with them? This preoperative screening helps to categorize patients this way, but it is inherently unreliable.

Ideally, all patients should be treated as POSITIVE and the neurosurgical team protect itself as much as possible. That protection involves using appropriate face masks and the personal protection equipment in the operating room. Of course, it is not as simple as this and the PPE can be uncomfortable for the surgeon and increase the risk of mistakes leading to morbidity or mortality for the patient. An uncomfortable surgical team will cut corners.

A face mask should also be worn by the team during other interactions with the patient outside of the operating room. Social distancing between a surgeon and the patient is not practical and there are so many other issues beyond what we can discuss in this article.

Overall, the best solution is to limit patient contact at the present time and manage only serious emergencies that leave no room for other than surgery. Life or limb threatening conditions like an extradural hematoma and cauda equina syndrome fall into this category.

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Submission Date

21/11/2020

Acceptance Date

29/12/2020

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